

Case Report

Fibrolipomatous Hamartoma Of Digital Branch Of Median Nerve: A Rare Case Report.

Meghana Deshmukh,¹ Bhavika Jain,² Nikhat Bano,³ Kavita Makasare,⁴ Saurabh Joshi⁵
P S Mishrikotkar,⁶ D.B Dahiphale⁷

Resident^{1,2,3}, Assistant Professor^{4,5}, Professor^{6,7} Department of Radio diagnosis MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad.

Corresponding Author: Dr Bhavika Jain.

Abstract:

Fibrolipomatous hamartoma of the nerve is a benign neoplasm resulting from growth of fibroadipose tissue of nerve sheaths. The other terminologies used for this entity include perineural lipoma, intraneural lipoma, and lipomatous hamartoma. Though any nerve can be involved, median nerve is reported to be affected in more than 50% of the cases. The other nerves which are commonly involved includes radial, ulnar, sciatic, and plantar nerves. Though it is believed to be present since birth they may clinically present in childhood or even in early adulthood. The imaging has an important role to play in the diagnosis of fibrolipomatous hamartoma. The diagnosis is usually made on the basis of ultrasound and MRI. Confirmation of diagnosis requires histopathological examination. Since its benign neoplasm the management is usually conservative.

We hereby report a case of 26-year-old male patient who presented with a slowly enlarging, painless swelling over the right palm involving the thenar eminence and extending to involve volar aspect of second and third digits for 1 year. The diagnosis was made on the basis of imaging (X-Ray, USG and MRI). Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis.

Keywords: Fibrolipomatous hamartoma (FLH), median nerve, ultrasonography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), macrodystrophia lipomatosa

INTRODUCTION:

Fibrolipomatous hamartoma (FLH) also known as neural fibrolipoma is a rare slow growing and benign tumor arising from peripheral nerve, median nerve being the most common site. The tumor is most commonly seen in young patients.¹ It is designated as Nervous lipomatosis according to the new World Health Organization (WHO) classification of tumors.² This tumor is very rare but imaging findings are so characteristic that it allows a confident diagnosis by a radiologist. Fibrolipomatous hamartoma (FLH) is nothing but an intraneural/perineural lipoma, that most

commonly affects the median nerve at or below the level of wrist joint.³

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 26-year-old male patient who presented with a slowly enlarging, painless swelling over the right palm involving the thenar eminence and extending to involve volar aspect of second and third digits for 1 year (Fig.1). There was macrodactyly of right second and third digits with paresthesia along the distribution of median nerve (Fig.2). Ultrasound was done as initial imaging modality by our team and it revealed characteristic findings of thickened echogenic

fatty tissue mass. Hypoechoic nerve fascicles were interspersed in between the abnormal hyperechoic fatty tissue mass (Fig.3). No vascularity was noted within and surrounding the mass on color Doppler imaging (Fig.4).

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) demonstrated a mass at the level of volar aspect of right palm extending to thenar eminence and up to second and third digits along the distribution of right median nerve where the palpable abnormality was felt on clinical examination.

The MRI demonstrated fusiform enlargement of the median nerve and its digital branches. T1 coronal images demonstrated long tubular hypointense structures representing thickened nerve fascicles with surrounding hyperintense tissue representing fat s/o “spaghetti string” appearance.

There was significant suppression of fat-on-fat suppressed images. On axial images there was characteristic “coaxial cable-like” appearance of the lesion. Keeping in mind all these characteristic and pathognomonic features diagnosis of Fibrolipomatous hamartoma with macrodystrophia lipomatosa was given. Histopathological correlation was also done and it also revealed hamartomatous growth (Fig 5,6,7).

Fig 1: Swelling over right palm involving the thenar eminence and extending to involve volar aspect of second and third digits with macrodactyly of right second and third digits (Compared with normal left hand).

Fig 2: Radiograph of right hand depicting soft tissue swelling and focal gigantism involving 2nd and 3rd digits (Yellow arrows).

Fig 3: Ultrasound depicting findings of thickened echogenic fatty tissue mass with hypoechoic nerve fascicles interspersed in between the abnormal hyperechoic fatty tissue mass (Yellow arrow).

Figure 4: Doppler Image showing no internal vascularity.

Fig 5: Coronal T1W MRI depicting hypointense thickened median nerve fascicles and hyperintense fatty tissue interspersed in between (arrow).

Figure 6: Coronal T1FSE MRI demonstrates significant suppression of fatty tissue surrounding the thickened tubular nerve fascicles (Arrow).

Fig 7: Axial weighted image with Fibro lipomatous hamartoma of the median nerve of hand shows thickened hypointense nerve fascicles surrounded by hyperintense fatty tissue giving “coaxial cable” appearance

Discussion: -

Here we, discuss the characteristic imaging findings of this rare benign tumor that are often pathognomonic. Fibroliopomatous hamartomas (FHL) are rare benign tumors usually young adults. The median nerve is the most commonly affected nerve and ulnar nerve being the second most common site (4,5).

Patient usually presents with soft, slowly growing mass over volar aspect of hand occasionally associated with focal gigantism and macrodactyly. Occasionally paresthesia along the distribution of median nerve can be experienced by the patient (6,7).

Exact pathogenesis is unknown, but it is postulated that it is a congenital abnormality and there is overgrowth of fibro fatty tissue which infiltrates the peripheral nerves causing its fusiform enlargement (8,9).

USG and MRI, both can be used to image Fibroliopomatous hamartoma however MRI is the preferred modality over USG for diagnosing Fibroliopomatous hamartomas. On USG it appears as hyperechoic tissue (echogenic fatty tissue) surrounding smooth round hypoechoic fascicles No vascularity was noted within and surrounding the mass on color Doppler imaging.

On MRI fusiform enlargement of the nerve fascicles can be seen. T1 coronal images demonstrates long tubular hypointense structures representing thickened nerve fascicles with surrounding hyperintense tissue representing fat s/o “spaghetti string” appearance. Significant suppression of fat-on-fat suppressed images is seen. On axial images there is characteristic “coaxial cable-like” appearance of the lesion (10)

Almost one quarter of cases are associated with a form of localized gigantism known as macro-dystrophia lipomatosis as in our case where 2nd and 3rd digits demonstrated hypertrophy of soft tissue and osseous structures.

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